

A STUDY ON IMPACT OF USAGE OF UPI PAYMENT AMONG THE STREET VENDORS IN COIMBATORE

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the impact of UPI (Unified Payments Interface) usage among street vendors in Coimbatore. With the increasing adoption of digital payment systems, UPI has emerged as a convenient and cost-effective mode of transaction. The research focuses on understanding the level of awareness, benefits, challenges, and changes in customer behavior due to UPI adoption. Data was collected through surveys conducted among selected street vendors across different areas of the city. The findings reveal a positive shift toward digital payments, enhanced transaction speed, and increased customer satisfaction, despite initial hurdles related to digital literacy and technical issues.

Keywords: UPI, transaction

1.1 INTRODUCTION

The Unified Payments Interface (UPI) is a ground-breaking digital payment system that has revolutionized how people manage their financial transactions in India and several other nations. Financial transactions are simplified as a result. UPI has gained enormous acclaim for its practicality, bank compatibility, and contribution to the development of India's cashless economy. Because it makes peer-to-peer transactions easier and makes merchant payments easier, it has emerged as a crucial part of the country's digital payment ecosystem. UPI is primarily a real-time payment system that enables users to send and receive funds from their bank accounts using a mobile app or a web interface. It makes financial transactions faster and more accessible by doing away with the need for conventional payment methods like cash or checks

1.1 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To analyse awareness of UPI payment towards street vendors.

- To analyse the preference of street vendors towards UPI payments.
- To analyse the advantages of UPI payments.
- To identify the level of satisfaction among street vendors in using UPI Apps.
- To understand the problems faced by street vendors in using UPI payments.

1.2 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

- The Study will cover the various aspects of impact of UPI payments daily life, including convenience, security, financial inclusion, the digital economy, small businesses, and government initiatives.
- The study will explore the challenges and opportunities UPI payments have presented to the street vendors in Coimbatore.
- The research will focus on looking at the aspects like customer satisfaction and their convenience towards using UPI payments.

1.3 LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The research will be limited to impact of UPI payments such as awareness, preference, advantages, level of satisfaction, challenges and problem faced among street vendors in Coimbatore only. It is limited to Coimbatore city only. The study is limited to 120 respondents

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Evin Foster, Scott Schuh, and Hanbing Zhang (2010) they examined the consumer payment methods with respect to cash holdings and withdrawals which was decreasing since 2010. There was an increase in card payment system with respect to 2009 in the year 2010, which resulted in less usage of paper currency. Since 2010 there was an increase in usage of debit and credit card compare to cash transaction which slowly took a decline giving rise to prepaid payments.

Singh.A et.al (2012) in their study discussed how secure the internet network should be to make smooth transaction for all the parties and the merchants. The systems are made in such a way so that there is no fraudulent activity takes place people can use their card for transaction in a secure way so that no data is shared. People mostly do digital transactions for e-commerce but they find internet I not secure to do so. Therefore some strict protocol should be followed and managed to make transaction secure

and the data is also protected.

Oladejo, Morufu et.al (2012) in their study examined the improvement of e-payment system in Nigeria. They explored what initiated the people to adopt the e-payment system. A structured questionnaire and some financial statements were collected to analyse the data. The results were such that when bank adopted e-payment system there was a change in the performance level of the banks. With the advent of e-payment system there was a rise in usage of ATMs.

Nitsure (2014) in his study highlighted the issues that were being faced or observed in developing country like India in using the e-payment system which was due to the low spread of internet and technology. The paper focused on major issues such as security, rules, etc. IN a country like India there is a high risk where the poor's are given a chance to be informed about such facilities neither they are given any such information.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter on research methodology took a look at the research background research design, population, sampling technique, sampling size, data collection procedure and data analysis.

RESEARCH DESIGN

A research design is a framework that provides a direction to the investigation being conducted in the most efficient manner. It provides a comprehensive and detailed explanation of the phenomena under the study. The research design used for this research is descriptive research design.

DESCRIPTIVE RESEARCH DESIGN

Descriptive research design uses a range of both qualitative research and quantitative data (although quantitative research is the primary research method) to gather information to make accurate predictions about a particular problem or hypothesis.

POPULATION OF THE STUDY: The population of the study covers only 121 street vendors among in Coimbatore.

SAMPLING TECHNIQUES: Non probability sampling technique under that convenience sampling was adopted.

SAMPLE SIZE : The sample size (or) no. of respondents is 121

METHODS OF DATA COLLECTION

The data have been collected in the ways Primary data collection. The primary data have been collected through questionnaire and discussion with respective respondents.

ANALYSIS: The analysis used for this research are Percentage analysis.

PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS

Percentage Analysis is used to find percentage value for all the different questions used.

Percentages are used to make comparison between two or more series of data. Percentage =

No. of respondents / Total respondents * 100

4. DATA ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION

TABLE NO 1: Table showing the reasons for preference of UPI payment of the respondents

S. NO	PREFERENCE	RESPONES	PERCENTAGE
1	Convenience and ease of use	34	28.1
2	Faster transaction times compared to cash	46	38
3	Encouraging digital transactions for accountability	23	19
4	Customer demand and preference	18	14.9
TOTAL		121	100

INTERPRETATION:

The above table indicates that the primary reasons for their preference for UPI payments are faster transaction times compared to cash (38%), convenience and ease of use (28.1%), and the desire to encourage digital transactions for accountability (19%), while smaller proportion (14.9%) cited customer demand and preference

CHART : Table showing the reasons for preference of UPI payment of the respondents

TABLE NO 2: Table showing the factors that encourage street vendors to increase their usage of UPI

S. NO	USAGE	RESPONSES	PERCENTAGE
1	Lower transaction fees or charges	25	20.6
2	Increased awareness about the benefits of UPI	54	44.6
3	Support and training for using UPI effectively	25	20.6
4	Incentives or rewards for using UPI	17	14.2
TOTAL		121	100

INTERPRETATION:

The above table shows that among street vendors, the key factors that would encourage them to increase their usage of UPI payments are increased awareness about the benefits of UPI (44.6%) and support and training for using UPI effectively (20.6%), with a smaller portion interested in lower transaction fees or charges (20.6%) and incentives or rewards (14.2%).

CHART NO 2 : Chart showing the factors that encourage street vendors to increase their usage of UPI

TABLE NO 3 : Table showing that UPI payment have positively/negatively impacted their business

S. NO	IMPACT	RESPONSES	PERCENTAGE
1	Yes	86	71
2	No	35	29
TOTAL		121	100

INTERPRETATION:

The table suggests that among street vendors, how UPI payment have impacted their business. With (71)% believing that using UPI apps for accepting payments has positively impacted their business, while (29%) not positively impacted their business.

CHART NO 3: Chart showing that UPI payment have positively/negatively impacted their business

5. FINDINGS

- The majority of the street vendors in the survey had selected faster transaction times compared to cash (38%) for the reason for reference of UPI payment
- The majority of the street vendors in the survey had selected UPI as method of payment currently using for their business (47.9%)
- The majority of the street vendors in the study experienced satisfied (41%) on the overall experience of using UPI payment.
- The majority of the street vendors in the survey have felt somewhat convenient (31.3%) using UPI than other mode of payment
- The majority of the street vendors in the survey reported on positive impact (71%).

6. SUGGESTIONS

- ✓ Ensure UPI apps and resources are available in local languages, making them more accessible to street vendors.
- ✓ Educate street vendors about UPI security practices to protect against fraud and cyber threats.
- ✓ Organize workshops to educate street vendors about UPI and how to use it effectively.
- ✓ Create networks or support groups where street vendors can learn from each other's

experiences with UPI.

7. CONCLUSION

The study was mainly focused on the acceptance of UPI payments among street food vendors. It also focused on how they got influenced for adoption of UPI payment services. In conclusion, UPI has had a significant and positive impact on street vendors in Coimbatore. It has improved efficiency, expanded customer bases, increased transparency, and enhanced security in their daily transactions. While there are challenges to overcome, the overall trend is towards a more digitized and efficient economy for both vendors and customers.

8. REFERENCES

1. National Payments Corporation of India (NPCI). (2023). *UPI Product Overview*. Retrieved from <https://www.npci.org.in/what-we-do/upi/product-overview>
2. Reserve Bank of India. (2023). *Report on Trends and Progress of Banking in India*. Retrieved from <https://www.rbi.org.in>
3. Ghosh, S. (2021). Adoption of digital payments by small vendors in urban India: Opportunities and challenges. *Journal of Financial Innovation and Technology*, 4(2), 88–97.
4. Sharma, R., & Gupta, A. (2020). Digital payments and financial inclusion: A study of small businesses in India. *International Journal of Management Studies*, 7(3), 55–62.
5. KPMG & Google India. (2019). *Digital Payments 2020: A Vision for the Future*. Retrieved from <https://home.kpmg/in/en/home/insights/2019/09/digital-payments-2020.html>.
6. Kumar, P., & Raj, S. (2022). Impact of UPI on micro and small enterprises in Tier-II cities. *South Asian Journal of Business and Management Cases*, 11(1), 23–32.